

Complex compounds of nickel(II) with bidentate heterocyclic ligands using both S and N as donor atoms

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New complex compounds of Ni^{II} with bidentate heterocyclic ligands (N, S) of dibenzofuran series (L) are presented. Analytical data, UV, visible, IR, EPR and NMR spectra, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements suggest that the compounds are of [NiLCl₂] type, with the square-planar geometry. A quantum-mechanical explanation for the electronic spectra of the free and coordinated ligands has been found using EHT-MO approach.

Attention has been paid by various research groups on the complexes formed by transition metals with heterocyclic thioamides that act as bidentate ligands using both sulfur and nitrogen as donor atoms¹. Theoretical considerations on the behaviour of sulfur as a donor atom have been presented earlier² which indicates $d\pi-d\pi$ bonds between metal and the ligands.

Ni^{II} is a typical representative of class (b) metal ion, form stable compounds with soft Lewis bases, like thioamides³. Bivalent nickel, with d^8 electronic configuration, exhibits a special affinity to sulfur, forming complex compounds both with aliphatic and aromatic thioamides⁴.

The purpose of the present work is to explain the structure of some new complex compounds of Ni^{II} with thioamides of dibenzofuran series⁵: 3-(2'-thioacetyl-amino)-dibenzofuran (TAADBF); 3-(2'-thiobenzoylamino)-dibenzofuran (TBADBF), 3-(2'-thiofuroylamino)-dibenzofuran (TFADBF), as well as 3-(2'-thiothenoylamino)-dibenzofuran (TTADBF), by taking into account the results of the physico-chemical and quantum-mechanical studies.

Results and discussion

All the complexes of Ni^{II} with these thioamides of the dibenzofuran series (TAADBF, TBADBF, TFADBF, TTADBF) have been prepared by following the procedure described by Jensen and Nielsen¹.

The complex compounds are microcrystalline coloured powders, having higher melting points than pure thioamides (Table 1). They are moderately stable with poor solubility both in polar and non-polar solvents.

The analytical data (Table 1) prove that these complex compounds are of the type [MLCl₂], where M = Ni^{II} and L = TAADBF, TBADBF, TFADBF, TTADBF. The molar conductivities ($1.08-1.44 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ in 10^{-4} DMF solution, at 22°C) show that all the complexes are non-electrolytes.

Data regarding the nature of the chemical bonds and the type of the atoms involved in the coordination were obtained from the infrared spectra of the complex compounds (Table 2) and the ligands.

The thioamide group is a complex vibrational group with characteristic bands in the 1650–600 cm^{-1} range⁶. The bands of the 3150–3030 cm^{-1} interval, characteristic for ν_{NH_2} , appear in complexes at lower frequencies than in the respective thioamide, and they are more flattened. These changes suggest that the NH₂ group participates in the coordination. The intensive band the the 1650–1600 cm^{-1} range, assigned to the stretching vibration of NH₂, appears in the complexes at lower frequency. The characteristic band of the thioamide at 1450 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{C-N, C-C}}$ coupling), appears in the complexes displaced towards higher frequencies and having a lower intensity. These changes may be explained by electronic migrations of the thioamidic group as a consequence of the coordination. Special consideration requires for the bond that exhibits peak at 1220 cm^{-1} , in which the frequency of the C=S bond has an important contribution. In complexes this band almost disappears. This confirms the participation of the sulfur atom as donor in the complex formation.

Another significant band is at 980–960 cm^{-1} , assigned to the stretching vibration of the NH₂ group, a band that

Table 1. Analytical, molar conductance and preparation details for the complex compounds

Complex compound	M.p (°C)	Appearance	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Analysis (%): Calcd. (Found)				
				C	H	N	S	Ni
[Ni(TAADBF)Cl ₂]	157	Redish brown Microcryst.	1.28	45.33 (45.28)	2.97 (2.54)	3.78 (3.83)	8.63 (8.72)	15.84 (15.52)
[Ni(TBADBF)Cl ₂]	182	Yellowish brown Microcryst.	1.44	53.07 (52.92)	3.07 (3.24)	3.26 (3.74)	7.45 (7.88)	13.67 (13.23)
[Ni(TFADBF)Cl ₂]	165	Yellowish orange Microcryst.	1.32	48.27 (48.51)	2.60 (2.15)	3.31 (3.08)	7.57 (7.93)	13.89 (13.46)
[Ni(TTADBF)Cl ₂]	174	Deep yellow Microcryst.	1.08	46.49 (46.41)	2.51 (2.46)	3.19 (3.10)	14.53 (14.45)	13.38 (13.02)

Table 2. Characteristic infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) of the ligand and complexes

Compound	3500–3000 ν_{NH_2}	1650–1600 δ_{NH_2}	1600–1650		1350–900		900–600	
			1600–1450 ν_{CN} coupling C–C	1450–1350 ν_{CN} coupling NH ₂	ν_{CS}	δ_{NH_2}	900–700 ν_{NCS}	700–600 $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$
TAADBF	3090w 2960i	1600w	1455i	1370i	1210i 1180i	958m	845i 722m	670m
TBADBF	3090w 2960i	1600m	1450i	1350i	1230i 1150i	942m	848i 720m	680i
TFADBF	3220i 3050sh 2860w	1600m	1460i	1360i	1210m 1185i	952i	840i 730i	660m
TTADBF	3300m 3250w	1600m	1529m 1458i	1360i	1220m 1180i	977m 945w	848m 722i	670m
[Ni(TAADBF)Cl ₂]	3150sh 2985w	1600w	1465w	1347w	1220w 1188sh	968sh	788m 710w	665w
[Ni(TBADBF)Cl ₂]	3120w 2990sh	1600w	1460m	1338sh	1220w 1167w	957sh	796m 718w	668w
[Ni(TFADBF)Cl ₂]	3270w 2880sh	1600w	1465w	1350w	1220w 1170sh	948sh	775m 722w	657w
[Ni(TTADBF)Cl ₂]	3370w 3280sh	1600w	1468w	1335sh	1220w 1185sh	965sh	765m 720w	665w

i = intense; m = medium; w = weak; sh = shoulder.

changes in the complexes, lowering its intensity and once more confirming the involvement of the NH₂ group in the coordination. In the ν_{NCS} , $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ range, the 680–630 cm^{-1} band is significant, generally assigned to the C=S vibration, which also changes in the complexes, lowering its intensity, thus confirming the opinion that the sulfur participates in bonding. In conclusion, IR spectral analysis indi-

cates the participation of both sulfur and nitrogen atoms of the thioamide group in coordination to the metal. In order to establish the coordination geometry of the new complex compounds, a spectral analysis in the visible and UV range was performed⁷. The bands observed in the electronic absorption spectra of the studied complexes were assigned according to Gray, Ballhausen⁸ and Vanquickenborne⁹. The

correlation of bands observed in the electronic spectra of the studied complexes with those of $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ prompts us to the following assignments presented in Table 3. The correspondence between the bands in the prepared complexes and the bands described for $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ leads to the conclusion that all the new compounds have the same square-planar geometry.

A quantum-mechanical interpretation of the absorption bands proper to the free and coordinated ligands also can give informations about the coordination of the heteroatoms to Ni^{II} . The structural formula of the free and coordinated ligands have been modeled on the computer. Their molecular geometry has been optimised using the Molecular Mechanics approach (MM^+), the cartesian coordinates of the atoms being used to perform EHT-MO calculation¹⁰. It has been shown that the electronic transitions in the spectra are due to an electron transfer from the electron lone pairs of the heteroatoms (sulfur and oxygen) to excited states of the molecule.

Table 3. Electronic spectra of the complex compounds in the UV and visible range

Complex compound	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	Assignment
$[\text{Ni}(\text{TAADBF})\text{Cl}_2]$	22300	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	30620	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	32500	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1u} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\pi^*)]$ (<i>C.T.</i>)
	35350	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2u} [a_{1g}(\sigma^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\pi^*)]$ (<i>C.T.</i>)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{TBADBF})\text{Cl}_2]$	22080	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	30460	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	32700	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1u} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\pi^*)]$ (<i>C.T.</i>)
	38420	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\pi^*)]$ (<i>C.T.</i>)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{TFADBF})\text{Cl}_2]$	21805	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	30522	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	38380	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\pi^*)]$ (<i>C.T.</i>)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{TTADBF})\text{Cl}_2]$	21200	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	30300	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$ (<i>d-d</i>)
	38300	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\pi^*)]$ (<i>C.T.</i>)

These transitions are shift toward higher wavenumbers for the coordinated ligand.

The shifts are caused either by the mixing with *d*-metal orbitals for the antibonding states or by the energy lowering of the electron lone pair of the heteroatoms after coordination, which is realised by means of the sulfur and nitrogen atoms.

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the free organic ligand TTADBF shows a signal at $\delta = 187.129$ ppm due to the

carbon atom from the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ group. In the spectra of the $[\text{Ni}(\text{TTADBF})\text{Cl}_2]$, the signal appears at lower value of the magnetic field (183.254 ppm) once again proving the involvement of the sulfur atom in the coordination. The ^1H NMR spectrum for this ligand shows a signal at $\delta = 11.75$ ppm, corresponding to the proton in the imido ($-\text{NH}$) group. It appears shifted in the spectrum of the complex compound, indicating again the involvement of the nitrogen atom in the coordination. Therefore, the coordinative σ -bonds are due to the S and N atoms in the thioamidic group.

Conclusions :

On the basis of all these results, obtained by elemental analysis, as well as UV-Vis, IR, EPR and NMR spectra, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements, the following structure are proposed for the square-planar complex compound $[\text{MLCl}_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{L} = \text{TAADBF}$ (I), TBADBF (II), TFADBF (III), TTADBF (IV) :

Experimental

Reagents : $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck p.a.), aqueous solution (0.02 M); TAADBF, TBADBF, TFADBF, TTADBF (double recrystallized), ethanolic solutions (0.02 M).

Instruments : The IR spectra ($400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-1600 Hewlett Packard instru-

ment in anhydrous KBr pellets. The electronic spectra (13000–45000 cm^{-1}) were obtained in 10^{-3} M acetone solutions, by using an Unicam UV 2-300 spectrophotometer, while the EPR spectra were registered in powder form at room temperature by means of an Art-5-Ifin spectrometer, that operates in X band, the modulation of magnetic field being 100 KHz, using Mn^{2+} as an internal standard ($g_3 = 2.03584$, $g_4 = 1.98040$, $H_3 = 3179.5$, $H_4 = 3268.5$). Both ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varion Gemini 300 BB. The molar conductivities were determined by using an OK-102 Radelkis conductivity meter, in 10^{-4} M DMF solutions, at 22°C. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed on a Gouy Balance at room temperature.

General procedure : The $[\text{NiLCl}_2]$ complex compounds, where L is the ligand (TAADBF, TBADBF, TFADBF, TTADBF) have been obtained by adding ethanolic solution of ligand L 0.02 M to aqueous solution of nickel dichloride 0.02 M in a 1 : 1 molar ratio. After settling for an hour, the formed precipitate has been filtered on a G_4 porosity glass filter, washed with 96% ethyl alcohol, with diethylether and finally dried under vacuum.

References

1. K. A. Jensen and P. H. Nielsen, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1966, **20**, 597; V. Mureşan, N. Mureşan and A. Reiss, *Polish J. Chem.*, 1993, **67**, 2113; V. Mureşan and N. Mureşan, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1994, **39**, 1041; V. Mureşan, S. Florea, A. Reiss and L. S. Mureşan, *Polish J. Chem.*, 1995, **69**, 385; V. Mureşan, A. Reiss, L. S. Sbîrnă, N. Mureşan and S. Floera, *Polish J. Chem.*, 1998, **72**, 2034; A. Kriza, A. Reiss, V. Mureşan and S. Florea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 405; V. Mureşan, L. S. Sbîrnă, S. Sbîrnă, C. I. Lepădatu and N. Mureşan, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2001, **48**, 439; L. S. Sbîrnă, S. Sbîrnă, C. I. Lepădatu, V. Mureşan and N. Mureşan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 409.
2. D. Negoiu, V. Mureşan and C. Fulea, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1973, **18**, 1749; D. Negoiu, V. Mureşan and S. Florea, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1973, **18**, 1875; V. Mureşan and N. Mureşan, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1993, **38**, 173.
3. R. V. Pearson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3533.
4. R. G. Pearson *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1968, **45**, 581, 643.
5. S. Florea, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1994, **39**, 1138.
6. H. O. Desseyn and M. A. Herman, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1967, **23A**, 2457.
7. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectra", Elsevier, New York, 1984, p. 530.
8. H. B. Gray and C. J. Ballhausen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
9. L. G. Vanquickenborne, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 796.
10. G. Calzaferri and M. Brande, *QPCE Bulletin*, 1992, **12**, 73.